

Implementando um programa de Conformidade Cooperativa no Brasil

Implementing a Cooperative Compliance Program in Brazil

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RESUMO

Confia é o programa brasileiro de Conformidade Cooperativa, concebido e administrado pela Receita Federal do Brasil (RFB). Lançado em 2021, objetiva mudar o paradigma na relação entre a administração tributária e os contribuintes, guiado por princípios como transparência, boa-fé, confiança mútua e cooperação. O objetivo é alcançar previsibilidade, segurança jurídica, aumentar a conformidade tributária e reduzir a litigiosidade. Ao aplicar o conceito de gestão de riscos e analisar o comportamento, o histórico de conformidade e o sistema de gestão de compliance tributário (SGCT) dos contribuintes, a administração tributária pode interagir com cada um de forma mais eficaz e eficiente. O Confia busca engajar os contribuintes de maneira proativa, contínua e sistêmica, aprimorando também os SGCT das empresas com foco na conformidade tributária. Assim, foi criado o Fórum de Diálogo Confia. As empresas participantes desse fórum puderam propor temas a serem discutidos por grupos técnicos, sugerindo melhorias para o desenho do programa. Foi realizado um teste de procedimentos, cuja participação foi voluntária e condicionada à adesão formal da empresa ao Fórum de Diálogo Confia e à assinatura do protocolo de cooperação. Em dezembro de 2023, foi lançado um programa piloto, com o objetivo de expandir o teste de procedimentos com critérios quantitativos e qualitativos. As empresas validadas foram convidadas a elaborar colaborativamente um plano de trabalho de conformidade, oferecendo previsibilidade aos contribuintes sobre os principais temas abordados pela administração tributária. Este artigo se concentra em descrever, analisar e prever os custos e resultados dessa experiência.

Palavras-chave: Conformidade. Fisco. Relacionamento. Confiança. Segurança jurídica.

ABSTRACT

Confia is the Brazilian Cooperative Compliance Program, conceived and administered by the Brazilian Federal Revenue Service (RFB). Launched in 2021, it aims to shift the paradigm in the relationship between tax administration and taxpayers, guided by principles such as transparency, good faith, mutual trust, and cooperation. The goal is to achieve predictability, legal certainty, to increase tax compliance and to reduce litigation. By applying the concept of risk management and analyzing the behavior, compliance records, and the tax control framework (TCF) of taxpayers, the Tax Administration can interact with each one in the most effective and efficient way. Confia seeks to engage taxpayers in a proactive, continuous, and systemic manner, also contributing to the improvement of companies' TCF with a focus on tax compliance. Thus, the Confia Dialogue Forum was created. Companies participating in that Forum could propose topics to be discussed by Technical Groups, suggesting improvements for the program's design. A Test of Procedures was conducted. Participation in this test was voluntary, contingent on the company formally joining Confia's Dialogue Forum and signing the Cooperation Protocol. In December 2023, a pilot program was launched to expand the procedural test with quantitative and qualitative criteria. Validated companies were invited to collaboratively prepare a compliance work plan, offering predictability to taxpayers about key issues addressed by the tax administration. This article focuses on describing, analyzing and predicting the costs and results of this experience.

Keywords: Cooperative Compliance. Tax administration. Relationship. Trust. Certainty

1 | Introduction

At the beginning of this century, Braithwaite (2001) highlighted that after decades of research on the performance of public administrations, a "battle" emerged between those in favor of a coercion-based approach and those advocating for voluntary compliance with rules.

That author noted that in the tax field, the difference between the effects of using deterrence or coercion techniques and employing an approach to encourage voluntary compliance with obligations was then unknown.

Braithwaite (2001) concluded that a holistic understanding of taxpayer behavior is necessary to increase tax compliance and that this would not be achieved by considering them individually, whether individuals or companies. Furthermore, it is necessary to consider the influence that various actors may have on taxpayer behavior. Some examples of influential actors are industry associations, families, consultants, lawyers, accountants, and international organizations, such as the OECD (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development).

One of the oldest cases of applying this approach is observed in the Australian Taxation Office (ATO)¹, which shows the importance of investing in the taxpayer segment where there is considerable consensus on "compliance", with a strong commitment to observing tax rules.

The Australian compliance model begins by viewing the taxpayer as a client influenced by various factors, such as business, technologies, and sociological, economic, and psychological aspects. From this understanding, the model seeks to identify the best strategy to increase the level of voluntary compliance with tax obligations for each taxpayer.

Although taxpayers are influenced by various factors, they can still be divided into segments with similar behavioral responses. This enables the tax administration to avoid using a completely personalized approach for each taxpayer but to develop types of approaches more appropriate for each segment.

Initially, the distribution of taxpayers by segments was conceived in the form of a pyramid, where at the base we would have the largest number of taxpayers, who

would be more prone to compliance, and higher up, we would find segments with fewer taxpayers, with less propensity for compliance. This representation became known as the "tax compliance pyramid."

No statistically significant study has been conducted on the distribution of Brazilian taxpayers concerning their propensity for tax compliance. However, based on interviews conducted with the Brazilian Federal Revenue Service (RFB) employees and taxpayers, Lamadrid (2020) collected perceptions suggesting that in Brazil *"the base of the [tax compliance] pyramid would not be so wide"* or that the pyramid *"would look more like a rectangle"* or even an *"inverted pyramid."* This perception may have led to the intensification of the crime-economy paradigm in this country.

Studying what would be the motivation for compliance, Kirchler (2009) says that it depends on subjective constructions of tax phenomena and talks about developing knowledge about collective tax behavior. However, Kirchler clarifies that this is hindered when tax laws are difficult to understand, which ends up making them of little interest to taxpayers in general.

In the tax field, compliance and cooperation are social dilemmas studied in various disciplines, and, for example, in mathematics and economics, the optimal strategy for rational individuals is not to cooperate. Therefore, it is necessary to be forced to cooperate through control mechanisms and severe sanctions in case of non-compliance.

Indeed, the probability of audits and fines plays a role in compliance. The point is that in the interaction between tax authorities and taxpayers, traditional economic models assume that they make strategic decisions, and the rational-economic model emphasizes taxpayers' predisposition to behave non-compliantly, suggesting control and punishment as educational measures.

Kirchler, however, cast doubt on this, clarifying that these models focus only on improving tax collection and do not consider, in any way, the relationship between taxpayers and tax authorities (the State), as well as aspects related to equity (tax justice). The relationship in pursuit of equity should be the main target, and the possible increase in tax revenue only a side effect.

According to the logic of behavioural economics - as Richard Thaler and Cass Sunstein argue in Nudge

(2008) – individuals do not always act in economically rational ways, and their behaviour is often shaped by cognitive biases, heuristics, and the structure of the decision-making environment. Therefore, aligning incentives effectively requires more than simply offering rewards or penalties—it involves designing the 'choice architecture' in a way that nudges individuals toward desired behaviours without restricting their freedom of choice.

Progressing on the issue of the relationship between tax authorities and taxpayers, the OECD (2013) issued a report that evolved from the proposal of an enhanced relationship between tax authorities and taxpayers, initiated in the 2008 Study (OECD, 2008), to cooperative compliance programs.

This 2013 OECD Report examines the relationship between the largest taxpayers and tax administrations to recommend a relationship based on trust and cooperation. Despite recognizing that the proposal from the 2008 Study remained valid, the 2013 Report identified some additional characteristics, such as the relevance of the so-called "tax control framework" (TCF) used by large companies, to provide objective bases for building trust between them and the tax authorities.

The TCF is a fundamental element for the functioning of cooperative compliance programs, and its necessary existence integrates, for the taxpayer, the costs to adhere to and maintain the program.

Thus, in brief synthesis, the 2013 Report (p. 57) states that the effectiveness of a company's internal control structure begins with the moral and ethical values of management and how the organization's management ensures the implementation of these values in daily operations. Designing, implementing, and maintaining an efficient and effective internal control system is essential for a company to achieve its strategic objectives. The part of this internal control system that ensures the accuracy and completeness of tax declarations and information is called the "tax control framework".

The 2013 Report (p. 59) adds that all stakeholders must be aware that having "tax control" means being in control of the tax consequences of all processes and transactions within a company, not just the tax procedures themselves. In other words, the "tax control framework" is the internal control of all processes and

transactions with possible tax consequences capable of detecting, documenting, and informing any tax-relevant risk to the tax authorities in a timely manner.

Furthermore, it is important to emphasize that cooperative compliance programs should highlight the benefits of positive behavior by taxpayers, providing those open to greater transparency with a higher level of certainty about their tax positions.

Therefore, it is difficult to deal with many taxpayers in this type of program. Considering that the Tax Administration needs to offer advantages, rewards, or administrative benefits in return, the more taxpayers involved, the more work (and costs) it will have to carry out.

Considering these theoretical basis and previous studies, the objective of this article is to describe, analyse and predict costs and results of designing, testing and implementing a Cooperative Compliance Program. The study also enables a comprehensive understanding of the program's design, implementation challenges, and its implications for tax governance in Brazil.

This research employs a qualitative methodology based on a case study, focusing on a practical initiative led by the RFB. The case under analysis is the implementation of a cooperative compliance program, in Brazil. Data collection included official documentation, program guidelines, and public reports issued by the RFB.

¹ AUSTRÁLIA. Australian Taxation Office. *How we help and influence taxpayers. Compliance model.* Available at: <https://www.ato.gov.au/about-ato/managing-the-tax-and-super-system/how-we-help-and-influence-taxpayers>. Visited on: Aug. 7, 2025.

2 | Measuring costs and benefits of cooperative compliance

In 2021, a Manual (Owens and Pemberton, 2021) was published based on research conducted at the Vienna University of Economics and Business, Austria. It matters to highlight that this manual proposes a methodology for measuring the costs and benefits of a cooperative compliance framework and, to this end, identifies some critical issues.

2.1 | There are no one-size-fits-all formulas

It should be considered that there are different structures in tax administrations, and depending on each one, the costs of implementing a cooperative compliance program (CCP) may vary.

It is necessary to map internal work processes and to identify the tools and methods used to measure, for example, the cost of ordinary and monitoring activities, guidance activities, audits, and internal reviews. After mapping these activities and tasks, the next step would be to separate those based on regulatory actions (enforced compliance), that is, those that are not voluntarily executed by the taxpayers themselves, from those related to the cooperative compliance structure, where the tax administration assists the taxpayer in voluntarily fulfilling tax obligations.

In this process, from the Tax Administration side, it is important to consider other actors who may be involved in the implementation of a CCP, because in addition to the obvious parties, which are the tax administration and the taxpayer, it is necessary to include tax consultants, lawyers, and accountants, whom the OECD called "tax intermediaries" (OECD, 2008), and other public administration bodies that could benefit from compliance programs or even have certain costs with their implementation.

From the taxpayers' point of view, it is important to have an idea of compliance costs, including those related to indirectly involved actors, such as associations, confederations or chambers of economic sectors, media, politicians, NGOs, etc.

The complexity of the tax system is not relevant for the evaluation of a CCP, by itself, and the program should aim to provide correct and relevant information, deal with risks, build trust, and provide legal certainty (Owens and Pemberton, 2021, p. 246/7).

2.2 | Costs and benefits should be evaluated comparatively

The costs and benefits of a CCP can be assessed through its comparison with the traditional approach. Specifically, regarding costs, one can compare the duration of different work processes of the tax administration when carried out through the

cooperative compliance approach and the traditional approach. For example, one could compare the duration of different audit processes for tax assessment or for establishing transfer prices. In audit processes, however, it is necessary to consider not only the duration of the audits themselves, but also its developments (long and expensive litigations).

The demonstration of costs and benefits can help promote legal, cultural, and procedural changes within a tax administration. These are issues that may require significant changes: equal treatment of taxpayers, the speed and binding nature of positions (rulings) on tax issues, and the sanctioning policy.

For the largest taxpayers, especially, given the need to make some initial investments during the implementation of CCP, the demonstration of costs and benefits is quite relevant in deciding whether to enter the program. For example, for these taxpayers, the reduction in the quantity and frequency of information required by the authorities is also a cost reduction factor.

2.3 | Benefits of transparency and dialogue

The Manual (Owens and Pemberton, 2021) identifies transparency as a critical issue. In Brazil, we noted the need to build legislation that provides for the possibility of voluntary disclosure of acts, transactions, or operations by the taxpayer.

By voluntarily disclosing an act, transaction, or operation, or presenting documents and explanations about a particular tax position in a cooperative and transparent manner, the taxpayer receives an administrative position (opinion, guidance) and has the option to follow it or not. If they do not follow it, they know that the risk of being challenged by the tax administration - through inspection and assessment - is likely and that litigation may arise.

The advantage for the taxpayer, if they are certain of the legitimacy of their position, is that for any eventual litigation, they already have an opinion from the tax administration and cannot be surprised by new arguments. The advantage for the tax administration is that it will know in advance about any "tax opportunities" that are being or will be employed by a taxpayer.

Tax planning usually involves the same elements. What makes them challenging or innovative is the way these elements are structured and on which provisions of the legislation or jurisprudence they are built. It is expected that other taxpayers will make the same use of structures, opportunities, or operations as those disclosed and discussed within the scope of the compliance program.

These "tax opportunities," which can be understood as tax planning that exploits static or dynamic gaps in the legislation but are initially lawful schemes, arise from weaknesses in the law or mismatches caused between one law and other laws, or by the mutation of legislation over time. They may originate from the perception of specialized professionals or from judicial decisions.

Moreover, these "tax opportunities" always aim to reduce the tax burden or postpone the payment of tax, bringing advantages to the taxpayer through the obvious cost reduction, but also competitive advantages in the market compared to other taxpayers.

By knowing them, the tax administration can propose the appropriate legal changes or adjustments to correct the gap or mismatch exploited in the legal system, having concrete information on how it will or could be exploited.

Additionally, if the taxpayer implements the planning and corrective action is needed by the administration, it already has prior knowledge of the entire operation, which simplifies the auditing work and reduces associated costs. Furthermore, it can verify if other taxpayers are employing the same procedure, making the activity of selection and credit assessment very efficient, and any eventual litigation should be limited to legal issues, based on the divergence of legal theses, since the factual issues have already been opened and discussed in the program environment.

In short, once a "tax opportunity" is identified, whether it arises from weaknesses, mismatches, or the dynamics in the legislation, or from judicial decisions that promote new interpretations, it is more advantageous for the taxpayer, who participates in the cooperative compliance program and has opened a dialogue channel with the tax administration, to obtain administrative positions on the matter and make a well-founded risk analysis. For the administration, in turn, prior knowledge is advantageous, compensating the cost of issuing a prior opinion with agility, security,

and knowledge in any subsequent assessment and litigation, both for a specific taxpayer participating in the program and for the entire universe of taxpayers who, due to their activities, characteristics, or operations, may be employing the same scheme or interpretation.

Even in cases where the tax administration suspects an act, transaction, or operation of the taxpayer based on information already in its systems, provided by the taxpayer themselves or by data cross-checks provided by third parties (monitoring), the above advantages are present if worked within the collaborative environment of the cooperative compliance program, verifying reasons to offer the opportunity for self-assessment.

It is important to highlight that for taxpayers participating in the program, the operations, transactions, and any non-compliance that may even generate collective interest do not deal with mere identifiable issues from cross-checking declarations, but rather complex issues that usually require long audit work, that is, avoiding them represents a significant cost reduction for the Administration. For the establishment of such issues, the prior preparation of the work plan is as important as provided in the pilot of the Confia program (RECEITA FEDERAL, 2024.2).

3 | The Confia program

3.1 | Context

To understand the premises, the conditions and the objectives of Confia Program, it is essential to note that Brazil has a myriad of tax laws and regulations that generate endless doubts about their interpretation and application.

Moreover, Brazilian tax legislation imposes a great deal of ancillary tax obligations to its taxpayers in the form of compulsory tax returns. Consequently, RFB holds a vast amount of direct information, based on various tax declarations, and indirect information, based on data cross-referencing reported by third parties. This, from the perspective of tax administration, is an advantage; however, from the perspective of taxpayers, it represents a high cost in terms of time and effort to comply with their tax obligations.

When Confia was initiated in 2021, the level of trust between tax authorities and taxpayers was perceived as low. The tax administration dealt with its largest taxpayers based on data cross-referencing, automation, and audit specialization. The annual increase in these procedures was recorded as a demonstration of effectiveness (Parada and Campos, 2024).

Because of these issues, Brazil had (and still has) a concerning and costly volume of tax litigation, either in the administrative sphere, according to the Ministry of Finance (2023), or in the judicial sphere (National Council of Justice - CNJ, 2022). Even though this situation is unacceptable, resolving it falls outside the scope of Confia. The program, however, can contribute to preventing it from worsening by helping to avoid new disputes. Its effects on this aspect, therefore, are long term and for the future.

Another relevant aspect to be noted is that RFB offers its most used services electronically and, whenever possible, in an automated manner. This optimizes the use of tax administration resources and users' time, if they fall within standard situations. When a taxpayer has a problem that does not fit into one of the services offered by digital channels and, especially, when the solution to this problem involves more than one technical area of the RFB, the taxpayer has difficulty being heard and having their problem resolved.

From the perspective of the Tax Administration, this way of working hinders a comprehensive view of the taxpayer and the design of a complete strategy, seeking maximum tax compliance.

This model also brings dissatisfaction for taxpayers. First, because they do not have predictability of the set of tax issues that will be addressed in each period and therefore cannot plan to adequately meet all the demands of the RFB. Second, because contacts with the RFB are made independently by areas or servers. Third, because conducting these works in a non-integrated manner sometimes generates inconsistencies and delay in the final decision, postponing the provision of legal certainty.

3.2 | International practices observed

In addition to the theoretical basis described on the introduction of this text, practical experiences of other countries were also used for the "design" of Confia,

standing out: Australia, the United Kingdom, the United States, Spain, Italy, and Sweden. Each of these jurisdictions has developed distinctive approaches that reflect their institutional contexts and strategic priorities.

Australia has implemented the Justified Trust and Combined Assurance programs, which focus on ex post risk-based reviews of large taxpayers, as well as the Annual Compliance Arrangement (ACA)², which emphasizes real-time, ex ante engagement with corporate taxpayers to ensure transparency and reduce disputes.

The United Kingdom pioneered the Business Risk Review (BRR)³ process, which classifies large businesses based on their tax risk and promotes open dialogue between HMRC and taxpayers. This model emphasizes trust, behavioral expectations, and early resolution of tax issues.

The United States developed the Compliance Assurance Process (CAP)⁴, a voluntary program that allows large corporations to work collaboratively with the IRS to resolve tax issues before filing returns. CAP is known for its structured timeline, transparency, and mutual benefits in reducing uncertainty and audit burdens.

Spain has adopted a cooperative compliance model through its Code of Good Tax Practices⁵, which fosters ethical tax behavior and institutional trust. Another key feature of the Spanish model is the establishment of a Dialogue Forum for Large Taxpayers, which serves as a platform for continuous communication and trust-building between the tax authority and major corporate taxpayers.

Italy introduced the Cooperative Compliance Regime (CCR)⁶ in 2015, targeting large businesses that voluntarily commit to transparency and internal tax control systems. The Italian model is notable for its legal framework that grants certain procedural benefits to compliant taxpayers.

Sweden initially launched the Fördjupad Samverkan (Enhanced Cooperation)⁷ initiative in 2011, later rebranded as Fördjupad Dialog (Enhanced Dialogue) in 2014. Despite of the Swedish Tax Agency's strong reputation and high levels of taxpayer trust, the program is widely regarded as a failed experiment. Key reasons include unclear operational guidelines, perceived unequal treatment among taxpayers, lack of

tangible benefits for participants, and resistance from multinational enterprises who questioned the value and fairness of the initiative.

As noted by Björklund Larsen (2019):

“In hindsight, there seems to be a consensus that the introduction of FS was too fast and somewhat sloppily executed. Several interviewees voiced the opinion that the Agency should perhaps have invited MNEs, the Confederation of Swedish Enterprise and tax advisors to discuss the initiatives in depth, so that the ideas might have been supported by stakeholders.”

This reflection underscores the importance of inclusive stakeholder engagement and strategic planning in the implementation of cooperative compliance models.

These international experiences have collectively shaped Confia and help explain some of its distinctive features, particularly the decision to build the program collaboratively with its target audience through a Dialogue Forum, as well as the pursuit of a formal legal framework to support its implementation.

² AUSTRALIA. Annual compliance arrangement (ACA). Available at: <https://www.ato.gov.au/businesses-and-organisations/corporate-tax-measures-and-assurance/large-business/compliance-and-governance/annual-compliance-arrangement>. Visited at: Aug, 7, 2025.

³ THE UNITED KINGDOM. HMRC internal manual. Tax Compliance Risk Management. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/hmrc-internal-manuals/tax-compliance-risk-management/tcrm3360>. Visited at: Aug, 7, 2025.

⁴ THE UNITED STATES. IRS. Compliance Assurance Process. Available at: <https://www.irs.gov/businesses/corporations/compliance-assurance-process>. Visited at: Aug, 7, 2025.

⁵ SPAIN. Código de Buenas Prácticas Tributarias. Available at: <https://sede.agenciatributaria.gob.es/Sede/colaborar-agencia-tributaria/relacion-cooperativa/foro-grandes-empresas/codigo-buenas-practicas-tributarias.html>. Visited at: Aug, 7, 2025.

⁶ ITALY. Regime di adempimento collaborativo - Che cos'è. Available at: <https://www.agenziaentrate.gov.it/portale/schede/agevolazioni/regime-di-adempimento-collaborativo/infogen-reg-adempimento-collaborativo>. Visited at: Aug, 7, 2025.

⁷ SWEDEN. TLV:s fördjupade samverkan. Available at: <https://www.tlv.se/lakemedelsforetag/utveckling-vardebaserad-prissattning/fordjupad-samverkan.html>. Visited at: Aug, 7, 2025.

3.3 | Confia's objectives

In this context, the main objective of Confia is to provide legal certainty by offering taxpayers interpretations and administrative positions quickly and timely to prevent litigation.

As highlighted earlier in this text, based on Kirchler's studies (2009), a cooperative compliance program does not seek goals of increased revenue collection, nor is this one of Confia's objectives. Any eventual increase in revenue would be a secondary effect of the program on the tax environment involving all taxpayers, participants or not. Thus, the idea is that Confia promotes tax compliance on a voluntary basis, reducing the need for corrective or repressive actions.

The RFB has various indicators and measurements (RECEITA FEDERAL, 2023.2) regarding the number of audit procedures, monitoring, risk treatment, and case judgments. Reducing these quantities while maintaining the level of revenue collection would already be a positive effect of the cooperative compliance program.

Following OECD's proposed cooperative compliance model, Confia is voluntary for taxpayers who meet its requirements. This is because it is not advisable to impose compulsory participation on taxpayers in a program that values cooperation, trust, and transparency. Since taxpayers decide if it is advantageous or not for them to enroll in the program, it is necessary to make it attractive to them. To that end, cooperative compliance programs often offer advantages of different natures. So far, Confia has offered, mainly, benefits of administrative and procedural nature to its participants. For example, a dedicated point of contact and a simplified process for the renewal of the negative certificate of federal tax debts. The provision of these services consumes working hours of RFB's employees and, thus, represents a relevant Confia cost for tax administration.

Besides this costs for the tax administration to provide additional services to taxpayers, other significant costs are related to the application of risk analysis techniques; the adjustments that were necessary in the organizational structure of the RFB and the cultural change initiatives; all of that need to be evaluated in relation to the benefits perceived and in relation to the cost of audit procedures, risk management, and

monitoring that would exist in without the cooperative compliance program.

Risk analysis is employed upon entry into the program, and continues throughout the taxpayer's participation in it, preventively and systematically, to measure the results and monitor the evolution of the program.

Currently, we are discussing the use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools such as clustering, explainability or interpretability – to justify risk classifications assigned; regression and classification models – to predict future taxpayer behavior; Supervised Machine Learning (SML) – to analyze data to identify patterns and make predictions; and reinforcement learning – to provide continuous feedback to adjust the SML model.

The internal structures of the tax authority also needed to be modified to create units⁸ and work processes to serve the companies in the program, in a uniform and harmonized manner. In some cases, participant companies also needed to modify the structure of their tax departments to meet the program's requirements.

Considering that the prevailing culture at RFB before Confia was that enforced compliance was the only alternative, it was (and still is) necessary to invest in cultural change both in the tax administration and among taxpayers (Parada and Campos, 2024). Confia sought to do this through training, internal and external communication actions and the Dialogue Forum.

⁸ As will be explained in section 3.4, however, these units were not created within the scheduled timeline.

3.4 | Governance

Inspired by the Spanish experience, the governance model chosen by the RFB for its cooperative compliance program as proposed by the OECD (2013 and 2016) was based on a Steering Committee and a Dialogue Forum.

Confia's Steering Committee is responsible for defining the guidelines for the creation and operation of Confia. It is composed of the senior management of RFB.

The act of establishing the Committee demonstrated concern with the issue of equality, for it stated that Confia aimed to promote benefits for the tax administration, taxpayers, and society, "while

maintaining equal tax treatment among taxpayers" (RECEITA FEDERAL, 2021.2). This is because questions about this fundamental principle of law in the application of cooperative compliance programs are common, as only some taxpayers will be admitted and will receive differentiated treatment from the tax administration.

To avoid repeating the missteps observed in the Swedish experience, the Dialogue Forum was created with the aim of involving the target audience of the cooperative compliance program in its development.

To this end, the RFB selected and invited a group of 40 large companies to participate in the Forum. These companies were selected based on objective criteria applied to RFB's own or public data. In addition, to increase the representation of the target audience in the design of the program, RFB also invited three industry associations that represent different segments of large taxpayers: the Brazilian Federation of Banks, the Brazilian Association of Publicly Traded Companies and the Applied Tax Studies Group.

The act of establishment of the Dialogue Forum for the Cooperative Tax Compliance Program (RECEITA FEDERAL, 2021) defined "*Cooperative Tax Compliance as a closer relationship, based on trust and transparency, between the RFB and taxpayers who have a consolidated structure of corporate tax governance, tax control, and risk management, with the aim of establishing mutual cooperation interests...*".

The mention of "corporate tax governance, tax control, and risk management" in the Forum's act of establishment is a clear indication that the program seeks to establish trust objectively justified by the existence of the tax control framework, as recommended by the OECD.

Within the governance model envisioned for the program, the role of the Dialogue Forum was to: i) study the cooperative compliance model advocated by the OECD, as well as practical experiences of programs in other countries, ii) identify the specific needs of Brazilian taxpayers and iii) discuss the feasibility and convenience of applying each solution in Brazil; to iv) develop proposals for a cooperative compliance program model that followed OECD guidelines while adapting to the Brazilian tax environment, with its specific peculiarities and challenges. Decisions about

these proposals were made by the Steering Committee of the program.

It is important to emphasize that Confia is not solely concerned with governance on the taxpayers' side and of the Confia Program, but also with the integrity of its officials' conduct. To mitigate the risk of 'sweetheart deals' that may arise from closer relationships between tax officials and taxpayers, the program adopts a series of preventive measures.

For instance, meetings with taxpayers are always conducted by pairs of tax officials, all meetings are documented in official minutes, and since most are held virtually, they are also recorded and archived. Additionally, there are supervisors assigned to groups of tax officials and a central operational coordination unit responsible for reviewing and harmonizing procedures.

All of this is supported by a robust institutional standard for information technology systems, recognized as one of the most advanced in the world among tax administrations, including in terms of security⁹.

⁹ BRAZIL. RECEITA FEDERAL. See as examples: [The Federal Revenue Service develops innovative technology capable of increasing the detection of tax and customs fraud and illegalities](https://www.gov.br/receitafederal/pt-br/assuntos/noticias/2024/setembro/receita-federal-desenvolve-tecnologia-inovadora-capaz-de-ampliar-a-deteccao-de-fraudes-e-ilegalidades-tributarias-e-aduaneiras). Available at: <https://www.gov.br/receitafederal/pt-br/assuntos/noticias/2024/setembro/receita-federal-desenvolve-tecnologia-inovadora-capaz-de-ampliar-a-deteccao-de-fraudes-e-ilegalidades-tributarias-e-aduaneiras> and [The Federal Revenue Service adopts artificial intelligence to intensify tax oversight with the Analytics Project](https://portaldocantabilista.com.br/receita-federal-adota-inteligencia-artificial-para-intensificar-fiscalizacao-tributaria-com-o-projeto-analytics/). Available at: <https://portaldocantabilista.com.br/receita-federal-adota-inteligencia-artificial-para-intensificar-fiscalizacao-tributaria-com-o-projeto-analytics/>.

4 | The pilot program

In December 2023, the pilot program was launched. The intention was to expand the Procedures Testing and to test a five-step opt-in process: self-assessment, application, validation, preparation of the compliance work plan, and certification (RECEITA FEDERAL, 2023), including criteria for participation.

The implementation of the Confia Pilot Program involved some preparatory steps, such as drafting administrative provisions to formalize the pilot program; training the RFB servants who would work on it; designing and operationalizing self-assessment and application tools for interested companies; and preparing roadmaps and manuals.

4.1 | Criteria and the principle of equality

The nature of cooperative compliance, in which the tax administration and the taxpayer cooperate in a trust-based relationship involving ongoing discussion about the taxpayer's tax positions, could, in principle, make programs with this structure a fertile ground for "special deals" for large corporations that participate.

Therefore, programs based on purely quantitative criteria (e.g., turnover or gross revenue), which designate large corporate taxpayers as eligible without any additional requirements, would not withstand a selectivity test¹⁰ and would violate the principle of equality.

Qualitative criteria - like a good record of tax compliance in the past, having corporate tax governance and a tax compliance management system in place, and the complexity of the structure and transactions carried out -, on the other hand, are more robust, even when applied in combination with quantitative factors (Szudoczky and Majdanska, 2017, p. 228/9).

This is why RFB chose to combine quantitative and qualitative criteria among the requirements to participate in the Confia Pilot.

Quantitative criteria included: i) gross revenue above two billion reais (BRL)¹¹; ii) total declared tax debts above one hundred million reais (BRL)¹²; and iii) total tax credits suspended due to being under administrative or judicial discussion to the declared gross revenue and assets ratios, as proxy to the risk appetite and litigation profile.

Qualitative criteria included the existence of the corporate tax governance structure and the regularity of tax payments and tax returns.

¹⁰ The "selectivity test" in the context of applying a principle of law generally refers to the criteria or standards used to determine whether a legal principle or rule should be applied in a specific case. This test helps ensure that the application of the law is fair, consistent, and appropriate to the circumstances. The test would assess factors such as the intent behind the law, its impact, and whether there is a legitimate governmental interest justifying the selective application.

¹¹ At 29.04.2025, 2 Billion BRL corresponds to 354 Million USD.

¹² At 29.04.2025, 100 Million BRL corresponds to 18 Million USD.

4.2 | Opt-in process

At the beginning of the opt-in process, taxpayers were required to perform a self-assessment to verify the adequacy of their policies and internal procedures to the objectives and requirements of Confia. After that, taxpayers who considered themselves eligible could, at their own discretion, apply for the program by electronically filling out forms and uploading documentation. Next, tax officials verified the information provided against the requirements in a validation step.

Taxpayers that met the requirements moved to the cooperative preparation of a Compliance Work Plan. This Work Plan was conceived as a response to the needs reported by taxpayers in the initial surveys carried out by the Dialogue Forum. More specifically, the Compliance Work Plan intends to provide predictability to taxpayers about the relevant tax issues that the tax administration intends to work on concerning each of the candidate companies during a predetermined period (RECEITA FEDERAL, 2024).

The RFB received¹³ 31 applications for the Confia pilot, 24 of which were validated and 20 of which were certified and are participating in the pilot to this day.

A satisfaction survey was conducted among taxpayers, and their assessment of the process was generally positive. From the RFB's perspective, the five step opt-in process also worked well, but some opportunities for simplification were identified, especially in the validation step.

¹³ Confia Pilot from RFB receives 31 applications. Available at: <https://www.jota.info/opiniao-e-analise/colunas/coluna-barbara-mengado/piloto-do-programa-confia-da-receita-recebe-31-inscricoes-15052024>

4.3 | Compliance work plans

The most complex and challenging step of the opt-in process was the preparation of the compliance work plan.

This step did not involve any direct financial investment, but it consumed hours of work from qualified professionals: Tax Auditors and Tax Analysts from the RFB and staff members from participating taxpayers. It is estimated that around 360 hours of work

were consumed in meetings to prepare the Work Plans. According to information collected from a survey of the taxpayers who participated in the process, most spent less than 24 hours on preparation and less than 24 hours on agreeing on the work plan.

The 2024 Compliance Work Plans were developed cooperatively and in dialogue with the candidate companies. It's important to note that not only RFB could bring tax issues to the Work Plan, but taxpayers were also encouraged to bring tax issues and doubts that they wish to resolve.

Identifying and prioritizing the tax issues of each taxpayer, in a comprehensive and integrated manner, was a challenging task because it goes against the organizational logic of the RFB, which is structured hierarchically and fragmented by work processes.

The solution found to overcome this challenge was the creation, for each taxpayer, of a Transversal Committee composed of representatives from Centro Confia and from the areas that are responsible for monitoring tax compliance, programming, inspections and collection.

In August 2024, 127 Tax Issues were agreed upon in the 20 Compliance Work Plans signed by companies and the RFB. These issues were classified into five topic groups: i) taxation on revenue; ii) taxation on profits; iii) social security contributions; iv) bookkeeping and declaration; and v) others.

The implementation of compliance work plans brought positive results but also difficulties. Of the 127 tax issues agreed upon in the 20 Compliance Work Plans, 35 were able to be concluded within the initially scheduled deadline of December 31, 2024. Another 62 were in progress and 30 could not be initiated.

To address the tax issues that could be initiated, 181 meetings were held, lasting 181 hours and involving 230 participants, including 105 RFB servants and 125 staff members from the taxpayers.

The execution of compliance work plans was negatively impacted by some external factors, over which the Confia Center had no control¹⁴.

¹⁴ A mobilization of tax auditors, led by the union, between November 2024 and July 2025; the non-implementation of an important adjustment in the structure of the RFB: five large taxpayer units, each containing representatives from all technical areas is expected to be

4.4 | Benefits of the Confia pilot

Even though partial, the execution of the Compliance Work Plans brought positive results for the RFB, for the participating taxpayers, and even for society at large. These positive results can be classified into the following broad categories:

1. internal harmonization of understandings within RFB and adoption of institutional positions regarding controversial topics;
2. provision of clear guidance to taxpayers on controversial topics, including through the improvement of relevant legislation;
3. regularization of non-compliances by taxpayers, with collections for the treasury and savings in penalties for the taxpayers involved; and
4. proposals for improving RFB work processes and taxpayers' governance.

Other general positive results of the execution of the Compliance Work Plans:

5. direct access and dialogue between taxpayers and the RFB through the Focal Points;
6. real-time work with taxpayers for the application of tax legislation, especially on topics subject to recent legislative changes;
7. clear and timely guidance to taxpayers on complex and specific issues in fulfilling their tax obligations;
8. dozens of renewals of negative certificate of federal tax debts, carried out in conjunction with taxpayers, without the need for judicial measures.

The controversial topics involved in these results included international issues like Transfer Pricing, Financial Expenses, Thin Capitalization, Worldwide Taxation, Exemption of Revenues of Financial Institutions, and Income Tax paid abroad.

Further results are expected with the completion of ongoing tax issues, specially building institutional positions of the Federal Revenue Service on other controversial topics.

4.5 | Costs of the Confia pilot

4.5.1 | Providing predictability and building trust

The preparation of the compliance work plan, which must address all the issues that the tax administration intends to deal with for a given taxpayer, requires coordination between various technical areas and the analysis of different types of risk.

Taking into consideration the size and the structure of the RFB, this integration and preparation of the plan, which serves as a unified approach to the relationship with a given taxpayer, requires changes in operational paradigms. This also represents a cost, which we could call the cost of providing predictability.

Similarly, adapting to Confia's requirements, especially of transparency and cooperation, and implementing a satisfactory governance structure represents an initial cost for the taxpayer who wishes to participate. This is essential for the Work Plan to achieve its expected results.

As already explained, cooperative compliance programs are voluntary, and taxpayers present their intention to participate. Taxpayers verify whether it will be advantageous or not to join the program, and the administration needs to offer services and procedures which add value to make the program attractive.

To this end, RFB did not need to increase structures but means and efforts needed to be shifted from an approach based on corrective actions to one based on preventive and guiding actions. This restructuring, depending on the administration's culture and the level of trust in the tax administration-taxpayer relationship, may have differentiated costs.

Thus, the size of the program is limited by the operational capacity of the administration to deal with taxpayers and offer these differentiated services efficiently and effectively.

4.5.2 | Cultural change

Another significant cost is that of cultural change (Parada and Campos, 2024), both on the part of the administration and the taxpayers, who tend to resist new processes and relationships. This brings about the need to invest in training, seminars, and capacity building, which represent a cost for the program's implementation.

It should be noted that although these costs are higher at the beginning, they do not disappear after the program is implemented and are ongoing throughout its duration, as studies (SILVA, 2024) in the Brazilian Authorized Economic Operator (AEO) Program demonstrate.

It is highly recommended to create a dialogue forum, with the participation of taxpayers, academia, industries, and market associations, for technical discussion about the program's foundations and even the sharing of ideas. This makes the proposal much better accepted when brought to administrative or political decision levels. Nonetheless, the creation and development of these forums are development costs of the program.

The role and size of the dialogue forum for discussing the compliance program must be well dimensioned and planned. Excesses can lead to very long discussions that end up hindering practical implementation. This decision requires study and knowledge of other programs.

It is also recommended that the program evolves gradually to address this cultural issue and the adaptation of the administration's structure. Therefore, cooperative compliance programs should be preceded by tests and pilot programs. However, this also produces a cost in terms of time and workload.

Nevertheless, this gradual and phased development brings benefits to the overall communication of the program, improvement of the relationship between the tax administration and taxpayers, development of its own regulatory framework, enhancement of corporate tax governance in candidate companies, and, most importantly, building mutual trust.

4.5.3 | Adapting the regulatory framework

As mentioned, the creation of a Dialogue Forum, a Steering Committee, a Procedures Testing, and Pilot program were all carried out through administrative acts.

Administrative acts, however, could not be used to implement an important adaptation needed in the tax fines regulatory framework.

The fines currently provided for in Brazilian law are high, have a punitive nature and aim to create a perception of risk within the logic of ex-post control. The dialogue and collaborative development of Confia program with taxpayers revealed that they would not feel comfortable in being transparent, specially to disclose their tax plannings, under the current Brazilian legal framework of tax proceedings and sanctions.

Thus, a bill was proposed for the definitive program. This is because in the Brazilian constitutional-tax system, some issues are exclusively dealt with by strict law, such as the deadline for tax payments and the application of penalties. To modify these points, legal changes are necessary.

In many situations, legislative changes have a political cost because discussions move from an exclusively technical environment to a political environment where other interests and forces operate.

Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate the cost of proposing legislative changes. It is suggested that they be limited to the minimum necessary to provide the bases, principles, and legal certainty to the compliance program, in its existence and purposes. The more provisions about a compliance program are placed in law, the more difficult it becomes to change and adapt them to the program's development, which, as we said, should be gradual and constant.

On the other hand, taxpayers may feel much more confident in participating when certain issues are inscribed in a formal law text, making it more robust, and this level of confidence is a benefit to the program. In short, it is necessary to find a balance in terms of costs and benefits, in this case, not of the program itself, but of how it will be established.

5 | Parameters to measure costs and benefits

Based on experiences in Confia, we have identified five groups of parameters that can be used to measure the costs and benefits of the program and that we intend to test in the next Confia stages. These five groups and their main indicators are listed in the following sections.

These parameters can be measured for Confia participants as a group or individually. They can then be compared to the same taxpayers' pre-Confia records and/or to a comparable control group.

5.1 | Compliance behaviour evolution

The frequency with which **tax returns** submitted by taxpayers participating in Confia are amended and the relative value of these amendments due to errors is expected to progressively decrease. The distortions and inconsistencies detected by RFB in these tax returns is also expected to decrease.

Analogously, the frequency with which **tax payments** are made late or with errors, as well as the relative value of these errors, is expected to decrease.

Furthermore, the number of **inspections**, as well as the number, complexity and relative value of the irregularities detected in these inspections, is also expected to decrease.

These expectations arise from the fact that to be in Confia, the taxpayer must have a tax control framework. This system will work to signal risks and prevent errors in the preparation of tax returns by taxpayers. Additionally, discussing tax issues transparently in advance through Confia can reduce compliance inconsistencies arising from misinterpretation of legislation.

5.2 | Risk management

The total time spent by different RFB technical areas on taxpayers participating in Confia to monitor, to identify and to correct inconsistencies is expected to decrease. Furthermore, an increase in the quality of risk profiling for all corporative taxpayers is expected.

These expectations stem from the premise that cooperative compliance programs involve voluntary disclosure and cooperation between taxpayers and tax authorities (Owens, J., & Pemberton, J. L., 2021). Based on this voluntary disclosure of issues with potential or significant tax risk, taxpayers reveal all the facts and circumstances involved, giving tax authorities the opportunity to better understand the complex transactions of large companies, their behaviour regarding tax issues, and have access to their accounting and tax control structures.

5.3 | Institutional improvement

The number of tax issues disclosed and the amount of relevant information (to the formulation of tax policies, improvements in legislation, or legal certainty) provided is expected to increase.

This is because It is expected that taxpayers will disclose areas of tax uncertainty, making it possible to track, quantify, and monitor the main tax issues arising from specific characteristics of the tax system, such as complex and ambiguous provisions. In this case, what is learned from one taxpayer is applied to the others, generating quality and efficiency gains.

5.4 | Litigation management

Time spent on litigation, number of litigation cases, the diversity of topics in litigation and the value of taxes in litigation are expected to decrease.

Taxpayers' behaviour in a CCP is monitored in real-time, close to taxable events. This allows, for example, legislative changes that impact the taxation of specific economic sectors to be discussed in advance between the tax authority and the taxpayer.

5.5 | Tax certainty

The number of advance pricing agreements (APAs) and of mutual agreement procedures (MAPs) as well as the total time spent on tax rulings and administrative decisions are expected to decrease for taxpayers participating in Confia.

These reductions are expected in the long term, as tax certainty increases.

6 | Conclusion

The Confia pilot has proven to be an excellent opportunity to validate and improve the cooperative compliance model developed for Brazil. It has provided valuable insights for the implementation of the definitive Confia Program.

Most cooperative compliance programs (OECD, 2013, p. 58) expect taxpayers to voluntarily disclose situations, transactions, structures, and tax planning that may cause uncertainties regarding the application of tax legislation. Similarly, it is possible for the Tax Administration to bring forward innovative, unknown, or unforeseen risk issues that may produce tax advantages contrary to the spirit of the law, defined by general characteristics, to be debated within the program.

In other words, there is a trade-off between transparency and certainty. Transparency serves as an instrument to strengthen trust between taxpayers and tax authorities.

A cooperative compliance framework can function to allow quick and targeted responses to promote the stability of the tax system. This will result from technical improvements that eliminate distortions arising from policies that could be linked to ad hoc formulations of tax laws.

In this reasoning, cooperative compliance, in addition to protecting and promoting equality, also promotes legal certainty and reduces the possibility of sanctions and litigation.

Comparative parameters are necessary to demonstrate to tax administration senior management and society that Confia makes rational sense. In this sense, they would justify the needed investments for Confia's consolidation, implementation and future expansion.

Once the issue of measuring cost-benefit indicators and the implementation and consolidation of Confia have been addressed, a new challenge emerges on the horizon. A recent tax reform introduced a Value Added Tax (VAT) on goods and services in Brazil. Despite the significance of the expected benefits, the reform brings innovations that have raised concerns. One of the main points of uncertainty lies in the shared competence over the VAT, which involves 26 states, the Federal District, and over five thousand municipalities managing a

single tax. In this context, it is crucial to explore the possibility of developing and implementing a cooperative compliance program based on the experience of the Confia program. Such a multilateral initiative would provide legal certainty, reduce litigation, harmonize procedures, and lower compliance costs for both tax administrations and participating taxpayers.

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